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EFFECTIVENESS OF USING LANGUAGE LABORATORY IN TEACHING ENGLISH AMONG VII STANDARD STUDENTS IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The present study is an attempt to study the effectiveness of using language laboratory in Teaching English among VII standard students in Coimbatore District. The sample consist of 64 students was taken up for the present study. Experimental method was used for the study. Collected data were analyzed. It is found that there is a significant means score difference between pre-test and post-test among the students. It proved that language laboratory supported positively when compared to traditional method. Teaching English through Language Laboratory is one of the appropriate and effective methods for teaching English.

Keywords:

language laboratory, Teaching English, teaching.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Education is very important for an individual's success in life. Education provides pupils teaching skills that prepare them physically, mentally, morally and socially for the world of work in later life. Education is the best investment for the people because well educated people have more opportunities to get a job which gives them satisfaction.

English is the most widely spoken language in the world in terms of the number of native speakers. It is a world language, because less than fifteen percent of the world population uses it. English is the major language of news and information in the world. The language laboratory is a very popular technical innovation. The word ‘Language laboratory’s first used in 1930 in a research article by RALPH H.WALTZ of Ohio state university, America. The use of language laboratory gained ground rapidly in the United Kingdom in 1960. Language laboratory affords opportunity for the students to hear the language spoken and to practice speaking the language

themselves with correct intonation, pronunciation, accent and fluency. The Language Laboratory sessions also include word games, quizzes, extemporaneous speaking, debates, skits etc.

2. NEED FOR THE STUDY

According to Robert Lado, the language laboratory is “The center of Language teaching and the teacher helps its operational activities by providing suitable materials and learning situations. We are living in modern world. Language laboratory has the capacity to transmit a complete lesson of prose or poetry. At present language laboratory has been increased and their impact on Educational field, it is a two-way teaching learning process which minimizes pupil’s mistakes. It also strengthens the learning of English among students so the investigator is interested to find out the Effectiveness of using Language Laboratory in English among students.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the study is to find out the effectiveness of using Language Laboratory in teaching English.

- To find out the significant difference in post-test score between male student who learnt through the conventional teaching method and male students who learnt through the Language Laboratory.
- To find out the significant difference in post-test score between female student who learnt through the conventional teaching method and female students who learnt through the Language Laboratory.
- To find out the significant difference in post-test score between male students and female students who learnt through the Multimedia teaching method.
- To find out the effectiveness of the Language Laboratory.

4. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The main aim in the research study was to find out the comparative effectiveness of teaching English with the help of textbook and by using language laboratory. In order to investigate the various dimensions of the general research problem.

- There is no significant difference between the post test score of Experimental Group and Control Group.
- There is no significant difference between the post test score of Boys and Girls in Experimental Group.
- There is no significant difference between the post test score of Experimental Group and Control Group for Boys.
- There is no significant difference between the post test score of Experimental Group and Control Group for Girls.

5. METHODOLOGY

The investigator used experimental method to study about the effectiveness of using English Language Laboratory of VII standard school students.

Sample: A total sample of 64 students was taken up for the present study. The investigator used to pre-test and post-test technique is used for the selection of sample. The stratification has been done on the basis of gender, pre-test and post-test.

Tool: The investigators developed a tool to measure the English Language Laboratory of VII standard school students.

6. DATA ANALYSIS

The data was collected by the investigator using the tool developed for this purpose. All the data were collected by the investigator. Thematic analysis was undertaken with all qualitative data. For quantitative data analysis basic Descriptive statistics will be calculated. Pre and post-training scores will be compared using t-test. The difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of experimental group is compared with the difference in the scores of pre and post test of control group.

7. RESULT

Table 1: Post test score of Experimental Group and Control Group

Groups	Mean	Standard Deviation	t – Value
Experiment group	69.38	10.46	6.06
Control group	54.59	8.96	

The significant of the mean difference is tested using t – test from the above table. It is clear that the calculated t – value (6.06) greater than the table value (2.66) for degrees of freedom 60 at 1% level of significance.

Table 2: Post test score of Boys and Girls in Experimental Group

Experimental group	Mean	Standard Deviation	t - Value
Boys	68.19	11.06	0.64
Girls	70.56	10.03	

The significant of the mean difference is tested using t – test from the above table. It is clear that the calculated t – value (0.64) is less than the table value (2.986) for degrees of freedom 14 at 1% level of significance.

Table 3: Post Score for Boys between Experiment Group and Control Group

Boys	Mean	Standard Deviation	t - Value
Experiment group	68.19	11.06	3.55
Control group	55.5	9.06	

The significant of the mean difference is tested using t – test from the above table. It is clear that the calculated t – value (3.55) greater than the table value (2.76) for degrees of freedom 33 at 1% level of significance.

Table 4: Post Score for Girls between Experiment Group and Control Group

Girls	Mean	Standard Deviation	t - value
Experiment group	70.56	10.03	4.98
Control group	53.69	9.13	

The significant of the mean difference is tested using t – test from the above table. It is clear that the calculated t – value (4.98) greater than the table value (2.82) for degrees of freedom 15 at 1% level of significance.

8. DISCUSSION AND FINDING

The main objective of this study is to find out the knowledge of VII standard students. The data were analyzed by applying descriptive and inferential statistics.

- There is significant difference between the post test score of Experimental Group and Control Group students.
- There is no significant difference between the post test score of Boys and Girls in Experimental Group.
- There is significant difference between the post test score of Experimental Group and Control Group for Boys.
- There is significant difference between the post test score of Experimental Group and Control Group for Girls.

9. CONCLUSION

From the result and findings of the present study is concluded that the language laboratory offers powerful techniques for teachers to help students to participate and interact with peer groups teaching through language laboratory solves many problems. The selected secondary school students have gained more knowledge on English through language laboratory. Further, language laboratory is convenient for low achievers and high achievers. The use of Language Laboratory impacts positively on the teaching of English language it should be made active in laboratory. We should try our best to make English as one of the linking subject. We can say that the use of English Laboratory may provide a key to success in English education field.

10. REFERENCES

- [1] Aggarwal, Y.P (2006). *Statistical Methods Concepts Application and Computation*, Sterling Publishing ((P) Ltd, New Delhi
- [2] Best, J.W & James (2005). *Research in Education*, Prentice Hall of India (P) Ltd., New Delhi.
- [3] Evangelin, Arulselvi (2009). *Teaching of General & Special English*.
- [4] GangaPadhya, (1999). *Effectiveness of Classroom & Tapan Kaut Techniques in relation to students*.
- [5] Golden, S. A. R. (2011). *Problems and Prospectus of Distance Learning*, Bharathidhasan University, 343- 344.
- [6] Leakey, J. (2001). *Evaluating CALL Laboratory*.

- [7] Oods, P.S. (2001). *Macromedia Flash 5 Developers Guide*. Tata McGraw-Hill.
- [8] Scaife, J . F & Bass, R.K.(1993). *Information Technology in Science and Technology Education*. Philadelphia: Open University Press.
- [9] Ward, A.W. (1994). *Multimedia learning: A school leader's guide*, Alexandria, V.A: National School Boards Association.